

INVESTIGATING THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN RESILIENCE AND ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE IN FILIPINO ADOLESCENTS: A QUANTITATIVE ANALYSIS

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ABSTRACT

Resilient adolescents often demonstrate adaptive behaviors, such as effective coping mechanisms, strong social support networks, and a positive self-concept, contributing to their ability to navigate challenges and succeed academically (Masten, 2014). These adaptive behaviors allow resilient youth to regulate emotions, focus on goals, and persevere despite setbacks (Luthar & Cicchetti, 2000). This adaptability is crucial for navigating the pressures and demands of adolescence, ultimately leading to greater academic success (Rutter, 1987). Through quantitative analysis, the research delves into the connection between resilience and academic performance in Filipino adolescents. Therefore, this study examines how resilience is connected to academic performance in Filipino adolescents through a quantitative method. In educational settings, it is essential to have resilience, which is the capacity to adjust and recover from obstacles, to succeed. The study explores resilience's effect on Filipino teenagers' academic performance. Furthermore, the research utilizes quantitative techniques to examine data gathered from Filipino teenagers, most likely through surveys or questionnaires assessing resilience and academic achievement. Thus, the examination will establish the magnitude and orientation of the relationship between these two variables.

Keywords: *resilience, academic performance, Filipino adolescents, quantitative analysis*

INTRODUCTION

Some factors contribute to academic success, and understanding them is essential. In this period of technological advancement, resilience has become an important psychological construct. Resilience means the ability to adjust to adversity constructively by an individual. In this context, Filipino teenagers confront different challenges, including socioeconomic disparities, cultural expectations, and academic pressures. Academic performance fluctuation among students in various community settings is a prevalent issue for students, administrators, and school counselors (Delestre, 2016). Several studies have shown resilience is important in determining students' performance (Mirza & Arif, 2018). This study explores the relationship between resilience and academic achievement to provide useful insights for educators, parents, and policymakers.

The relationship between resilience and academic achievement among Filipino adolescents will be examined quantitatively. In this study, the researchers will assess resilience factors such as coping strategies, self-efficacy, and social support. The researchers will also identify patterns that influence their performance in school. Additionally, the study will explore potential moderating variables, such as gender and school environment.

The results of this research help enhance understanding of the factors that impact academic performance in Filipino teenagers. This study can guide the creation of programs that enhance resilience in Filipino youth, to improve their academic performance.

Due to the pandemic, Filipino teenagers face various emotional challenges due to exposure to social media platforms and the changing socio-economic environment. Filipino adolescents say that some students use grit to deal with adversities, while others lack the necessary skills to overcome challenges.

Adolescents face academic difficulties, societal expectations, and self-discovery during this important developmental stage. Teenagers in the Philippines, like all others, encounter particular challenges that can influence how well they perform in school. This research explores how resilience may impact the academic performance of Filipino teenagers.

In the Philippines, education is given top priority; however, students face numerous challenges and grapple with various hurdles. Socioeconomic factors such as poverty and a lack of resources may impede quality education access and lead to a challenging learning atmosphere. Furthermore, societal values that prioritize group unity and expectations from parents can contribute to the academic pressure to excel.

Resilience, which is the capacity of an individual to adjust and bounce back from challenges, is crucial for achieving success in academics, as stated by Wu in 2013. Various factors, such as genetics, epigenetics, development, psychosocial influences, and neurochemical elements, play a role in influencing it (Wu, 2013). Factors that provide protection and support, like self-regulation abilities, positive parenting, community

support, and quality education, are essential for developing resilience (Masten, 2009; Cutuli, 2018). Furthermore, resilience is crucial for job longevity in teaching and can be improved by evaluating challenges, understanding how to cope with them, and finding effective solutions (Bobek, 2002).

It is also the capacity to adjust to and recover from challenges. In an academic setting, resilient adolescents can handle stress, conquer obstacles, and stay motivated even when faced with adversity. Research has demonstrated a beneficial connection between resilience and academic success among different cultural groups.

Research indicates that resilience plays a key role in academic achievement, though there is limited information on this matter, especially among Filipino adolescents. Understanding this relationship within the Philippine setting is crucial. Family dynamics, cultural values, and educational systems are resilience factors that have demonstrated their influence on academic success.

Studying the connection between resilience and academic achievement in Filipino adolescents can offer important understanding. We can create specialized interventions and support systems by pinpointing the particular elements of resilience that play a role in achieving academic success. This can help Filipino teenagers overcome academic obstacles, creating a stronger and more successful student community.

Research Questions

The primary objective of this study is to investigate the relationship between resilience and academic achievement among Filipino teenagers. To achieve this objective, this study answered the following specific questions:

1. How do resilience levels differ between boy and girl Filipino adolescents, and how does this difference quantitatively impact their academic performance?
2. Is there a significant difference between Filipino adolescents with high resilience and those with low resilience levels?
3. Do Filipino adolescents with specific resilience factors exhibit significantly different academic performance levels compared to those without these factors?

METHODOLOGY

This research utilized a quantitative research methodology. Three hundred sixty Filipino adolescents from public and private schools, aged eleven to seventeen, were gathered as participants through an online platform with help from their class advisers. They filled out a validated survey instrument called the Student Resilience Survey based on CORC (SRS, 2016) and modified its format for this study. The survey includes a 40-question assessment with 10 subscales that gauge how students view their traits and the supportive elements in their surroundings. Self-esteem, empathy, problem-solving, goals and aspirations, family connection, school connection, community connection, autonomy

experience, meaningful participation in community activity, and peer support. A 5-point scale was used to rate each item (*1 = never, 2 = rarely, 3 = sometimes, 4 = often, 5 = always*). The participants were selected using a basic homogeneous random sampling technique based on the adolescents' age.

To measure the resilience and academic performance of the participants, resilience inventories were also supported by their average grades for the school year 2023–2024. The information was analyzed statistically to understand the connection between the variables. The basic information was obtained utilizing descriptives and frequencies, and the associations and impacts were analyzed using ANOVA, correlation, and linear regression techniques as well. Moreover, to calculate descriptive statistics, correlation analysis, analysis of variance, and t-tests, the SPSS 22 program is used.

RESULTS

Research Question #1:

How do resilience levels differ between boy and girl Filipino adolescents, and how does this difference quantitatively impact their academic performance?

In this study, the focus was on examining the relationship between resilience and academic achievement in Filipino adolescents. For the resilience factors in family connection, Table 1.1 displays the weighted mean scores, frequencies, and standard deviations differentiated by gender. The findings indicate that girls exhibit higher resilience scores in the family connection domain than boys. There is variability in the responses, with the highest responses in subscale 1 and the lowest in subscale 3. Overall, the data suggests that most items show a tendency toward more frequent "often" occurrences concerning the family connection factor across the entire sample.

Table 1.1: Comparison of resilience factors between boys and girls in the family connection

Gender	<i>Factors</i> Family Connection			
	<i>At home, there is an adult who is interested in my schoolwork</i>	<i>At home, there is an adult who believes that I will be a success</i>	<i>At home, there is an adult who wants me to do my best</i>	<i>At home, there is an adult who listens to me when I have something to say</i>
	Weighted Mean and Level of Frequency			
Boys N = 180	2.71 Sometimes	3.52 Often	3.76 Often	3.18 Sometimes
Girls N = 180	3.48 Sometimes	4.33 Often	4.48 Often	3.65 Sometimes
Total N=360	3.09 Sometimes	3.92 Often	4.12 Often	3.42 Often
Std. Deviation	1.239	1.024	.868	1.124

The data in Table 1.2 reveals that, in comparison to boys, girls tend to report a higher frequency of school connections. The overall pattern across all subscales shows a tendency towards more frequent occurrences of 'often' in the entire sample. Subscale 2 exhibits the highest frequency, while subscale 4 shows the least. These findings suggest that girls may perceive or mention these subcategories more frequently than boys, potentially influenced by the school context.

Table 1.2: Comparison of resilience factors between boys and girls in school

Gender	Factors School Connection			
	At school, there is an adult who <i>cares about me</i>	At school, there is an adult who <i>tells me when I do a good job</i>	At school, there is an adult who <i>listens to me when I have something to say</i>	At school, there is an adult who <i>believes that I will be a success</i>
	Weighted Mean and Level of Frequency			
Boys N = 180	3.37 Sometimes	3.33 Sometimes	3.40 Often	3.46 subscale 3
Girls N = 180	4.28 Often	4.08 Often	3.92 Often	4.34 Often
Total N=360	3.83 Often	3.71 Often	3.66 Often	3.90 Often
Std. Deviation	1.053	1.054	1.022	1.009

connection

In examining community connection as a contributing factor, it is notable that Table 1.3 demonstrates significant gender discrepancies in the assessed subscales through frequencies, with consistently higher frequencies reported by girls across all items. The overall data indicates that “often” is the more commonly reported frequency across all subscales, suggesting that these experiences are prevalent among the population. Although there are slight variations in responses, indicating a considerable degree of consistency in how participants perceive or experience specific events, some subscales show more variability in the responses. Hence, this analysis underscores the importance of considering gender disparities, given the widespread occurrence of these situations in the community.

Table 1.3: Comparison of resilience factors between boys and girls in the community connection

Gender	<i>Factors</i> Community Connection			
	Away from school, there is an adult who <i>cares about me</i>	Away from school, there is an adult who <i>tells me when I do a good job</i>	Away from school, there is an adult who <i>believes that I will be a success</i>	Away from school, there is an adult who <i>I trust</i>
	Weighted Mean and Level of Frequency			
Boys N = 180	3.29 Sometimes	3.09 Sometimes	3.42 Often	3.24 Sometimes
Girls N = 180	3.99 Often	3.89 Often	4.11 Often	3.96 Often
Total N=360	3.64 Often	3.49 Often	3.76 Often	3.60 Often
Std. Deviation	1.065	1.168	1.027	1.184

The findings in Table 1.4 demonstrate substantial gender-related differences in the factors linked to self-esteem, with girls indicating higher occurrences. The overall data shows in this table that the experiences measured are prevalent among the participants. The diversity in responses, especially for subscale 1, indicates the extensive array of individual experiences. These outcomes emphasize the importance of considering gender disparities and individual experiences when interpreting and utilizing this data in the future.

Table 1.4: Comparison of resilience factors between boys and girls in self-esteem

Gender	Factors Self-esteem Are there students at your school who would			
	<i>Tell you you're their friend</i>	<i>Ask you to join in when you are all alone</i>	<i>Tell your secrets</i>	<i>I can do most things if I try</i>
	Weighted Mean and Level of Frequency			
Male N = 180	3.49 Often	3.21 Sometimes	2.27 Sometimes	3.22 Sometimes
Female N = 180	4.52 Often	3.79 Often	3.14 Sometimes	3.86 Often
Total N=360	4.01 Often	3.50 Often	2.71 Sometimes	3.54 Often
Std. Deviation	2.885	1.220	1.393	1.016

The data presented in Table 1.5 reveals a significant gender gap in empathy. The participation of girls led to an increase in the number of subscales considered. The data overwhelmingly suggests that girls commonly reported experiencing the subscales, and the variability in responses ranged from minimal to very slight, indicating a reasonable level of consistency in how individuals perceive and respond to specific circumstances.

Table 1.5: Comparison of resilience factors between boys and girls in empathy

Gender	<i>Factors Empathy</i>			
	<i>Choose you on their team at school</i>	<i>Make you feel better if something is bothering you</i>	<i>I feel bad when someone gets their feelings hurt</i>	<i>I try to understand what other people feel</i>
	Mean and Level of Frequency			
Boys N = 180	3.00 Sometimes	3.27 Sometimes	3.42 Often	3.49 Often
Girls N = 180	3.56 Often	3.66 Often	4.18 Often	4.25 Often
Total N=360	3.28 Sometimes	3.46 Often	3.80 Often	3.87 Often
Std. Deviation	1.152	1.191	1.044	.969

The results presented in Table 1.6 highlight a significant gender gap in problem-solving factors, with a consistent increase reported by girls across all subscales. The collective data indicates that subscales 1 and 2 are commonly encountered, while the others are only sporadically reported. The responses vary widely, ranging from slight to high. Additionally, the high variability of responses in a broader range of human experiences underscores the need for strategies.

Table 1.6: Comparison of resilience factors between boys and girls in problem-solving

Gender	<i>Factors</i> Problem-Solving			
	<i>I can work out my problems</i>	<i>When I need help, I find someone to talk to</i>	<i>I know where to go for help when I have problems</i>	<i>I try to work out problems by talking to them</i>
	Weighted Mean and Level of Frequency			
Boys N = 180	3.15 Sometimes	2.69 Sometimes	2.85 Sometimes	2.72 Sometimes
Girls N = 180	3.65 Often	3.65 Often	3.52 Often	3.41 Often
Total N=360	3.40 Often	3.17 Sometimes	3.19 Sometimes	3.06 Sometimes
Std. Deviation	1.097	1.294	1.319	1.292

In Table 1.7, a notable gender disparity in goals and aspirations is evident, as girls consistently indicate a higher frequency for each subscale. The collective data indicates that subscales 3 and 4 are generally perceived as “often,” while subscales 1 and 2 are reported as “sometimes.” The moderate variations in responses underscore a wide spectrum of individual experiences and gender differences.

Table 1.7: Comparison of resilience factors between boys and girls in goals and aspirations

Gender	Factors Goals and Aspirations			
	<i>I do things at home that make a difference (i.e. make things better)</i>	<i>I do things at school that make a difference (i.e. make things better)</i>	<i>I have goals and plans for the future</i>	<i>I think I will be successful when I grow up</i>
	Weighted Mean and Level of Frequency			
Boys N = 180	2.86 Sometimes	2.77 Sometimes	3.42 Often	3.31 Sometimes
Girls N =180	3.57 Often	3.56 Often	4.29 Often	4.27 Often
Total N=360	3.22 Sometimes	3.17 Sometimes	3.86 Often	3.79 Often
Std. Deviation	1.123	1.084	1.046	1.057

The analysis of the data presented in Table 1.8 indicates gender disparities in autonomy experience, with girls reporting higher levels on subscales 2 and 4 compared to boys. The collective data suggests that subscale 4 is commonly experienced “often,” while the other subscales are experienced “sometimes.” The considerable variance of experiences among the participants in responses to subscale 1 points to a wide range. Hence, these results underscore the importance of delving deeper into the data to examine distinctions between boys’ and girls’ experiences.

Table 1.8: Comparison of resilience factors between boys and girls in autonomy experience

Gender	Factors Autonomy Experience			
	<i>I am a member of a club, sports team, church group, or other group</i>	<i>I take lessons in music, art, and sports, or have a hobby</i>	<i>At school, I decide things like class activities or rules</i>	<i>There are many things that I do well</i>
	Weighted Mean and Level of Frequency			
Boys N = 180	3.01 Sometimes	3.20 Sometimes	2.43 Sometimes	2.98 Sometimes
Girls N = 180	2.81 Sometimes	3.58 Often	3.12 Sometimes	3.87 Often
Total N=360	2.91 Sometimes	3.39 Sometimes	2.77 Sometimes	3.43 Often
Std. Deviation	2.146	1.208	1.263	1.042

The data presented in Table 9 indicates significant differences in the participation of girls and boys in community activities. It shows that girls consistently report higher frequencies for all subscales, indicating a notable gender gap. Subscales 1 and 3 are encountered “often,” while subscales 2 and 4 are encountered “sometimes,” demonstrating a range of experiences. Whilst, the results emphasize the relevance of considering gender-specific variations and diverse experiences in future applications of this data.

Table 1.9: Comparison of resilience factors between boys and girls in meaningful participation in community activities

Gender	<p style="text-align: center;"><i>Factors</i></p> <p style="text-align: center;">Meaningful Participation in Community Activities</p> <p style="text-align: center;"><i>Are there students at your school who would</i></p>			
	<i>Explain the rules of a game if you don't understand them</i>	<i>invite you to their home</i>	<i>Pick you for a partner</i>	<i>I help my family make decisions</i>
	Weighted Mean and Level of Frequency			
Boys N = 180	3.36 Sometimes	2.86 Sometimes	3.23 Sometimes	2.83 Sometimes
Girls N = 180	4.09 Often	3.46 Often	3.68 Often	3.47 Often
Total N=360	3.73 Often	3.16 Sometimes	3.45 Often	3.15 Sometimes
Std. Deviation	1.092	1.288	1.203	1.118

The data analysis presented in Table 1.10 indicates significant gender disparities in peer support factors, with girls consistently reporting higher rates across all measures. The overall data in this table shows that most participants experience subscales 1, 2, and 4 “often,” while subscale 3 is experienced “sometimes” by the majority. The variation in response rates suggests a wide range of personal experiences, and these findings underscore the importance of considering gender-specific characteristics and diverse experiences of the participants.

Table 10: Comparison of resilience factors between boys and girls in peer support

Gender	Factors Peer Support Are there students at your school who would			
	<i>share things with you</i>	<i>help you if you hurt yourself</i>	<i>I would miss you if you weren't at school</i>	<i>help you if other students are being mean to you</i>
	Weighted Mean and Level of Frequency			
Boys N = 180	3.46 Often	3.36 Sometimes	3.09 Sometimes	3.23 Sometimes
Girls N = 180	4.17 Often	3.79 Often	3.50 Often	3.72 Often
Total N=360	3.81 Often	3.57 Often	3.30 Sometimes	3.47 Often
Std. Deviation	.999	1.112	1.277	1.137

The data presented in Table 1.11 demonstrates that boys have a lower weighted average mean (3.13) compared to girls (3.82), indicating that, on average, girls are outperforming boys in this particular measure. The standard deviation results reveal that the boys' scores are more closely clustered around the mean, while the girls' scores are more widely spread. Although the higher mean for girls suggests better average performance, the higher standard deviation implies a wider range of performance among girls. This variability may indicate that while some girls achieve very high scores, others may score much lower, resulting in a greater disparity within the group.

On the other hand, the boys' scores are more consistent but lower on average. This could indicate a more uniform level of performance among boys, with fewer high and low extremes compared to the girls. Overall, while girls show higher average performance, the variability in their scores is also greater.

Table 1.11: Summary of the comparison of resilience factors between boys and girls

Group Statistics			
Resilience Factors	Gender	Average Mean	Average Std. Deviation
Home Connection	<i>Boys</i>	3.29	0.823
	<i>Girls</i>	3.99	1.138
School Connection	<i>Boys</i>	3.39	0.832
	<i>Girls</i>	4.16	1.070
Community Connection	<i>Boys</i>	3.26	0.865
	<i>Girls</i>	3.99	1.208
Self-Esteem	<i>Boys</i>	3.05	0.949
	<i>Girls</i>	3.83	1.968
Empathy	<i>Boys</i>	3.30	0.865
	<i>Girls</i>	3.91	1.191
Problem-Solving	<i>Boys</i>	2.85	0.995
	<i>Girls</i>	3.56	1.372
Goals and Aspiration	<i>Boys</i>	3.09	0.877
	<i>Girls</i>	3.92	1.096
Autonomy Experience	<i>Boys</i>	2.91	1.012
	<i>Girls</i>	3.35	1.646
Meaningful Participation in Community	<i>Boys</i>	3.07	0.985
	<i>Girls</i>	3.68	1.267
Peer Support	<i>Boys</i>	3.29	0.932
	<i>Girls</i>	3.80	1.245
Total	<i>Boys</i>	3.13	0.911
	<i>Girls</i>	3.82	1.328

The data presented in Table 1.12 shows that the average grade of 87.47 suggests that the overall performance of the students is quite high. The median grade of 88 and the relatively symmetrical distribution of grades around the median signify a balanced performance across the board. The range of 23 points, with the highest average grade reported being 97 and the lowest grade of 74, demonstrates a considerable spread in the grades achieved. The most common average grade level is 91, achieved by 9.2% of students, followed closely by a grade of 84 with 8.9%, and grades of 94 and 90, each with 6.9%. Conversely, the least common average grade is 97, achieved by only 0.6% of students, indicating relatively few students reach this high level of performance. Grades 74, 75, and 76 are rare, each achieved by only 0.3% of students.

The distribution of grades shows that most adolescents perform well, with a significant percentage achieving grades in the low to mid-90s. Few students excel with a grade of 97, while a small percentage of teenagers have grades lower than 76.

This study indicates that although academic performance is generally positive, there are chances for enhancement, especially for students with lower grades. Examining the elements that play a role in high and low achievements could help in creating approaches to assist all students in achieving their academic best.

Table 1.12: Students' Academic Performance based on their average grade

Students' Academic Performance based on their Average Grade Average Grade = 87.47 Median = 88 Highest Average = 97 Lowest Average = 74			
Average Grade (Most)	Percentage	Average Grade (Least)	Percentage
91	9.2%	97	0.6%
84	8.9%	74	0.3%
94	6.9%	76	0.3%
90	6.9%	75	0.3%
93	6.7%		

Research Question #2

Is there a significant difference between Filipino adolescents with high resilience and those with low resilience levels?

Table 2: Mean comparison between high and low resilience levels results of T-Test

Variables	F	Sig	t	df
Resilience Factors	14.039	.000	.069	358

Resilience is one factor influencing adolescents' well-being, or the specific measures used weren't sensitive enough to capture the nuances of resilience in a Filipino context. The findings reveal that there is no identifiable distinction between Filipino teenagers who have high resilience and those with low resilience levels. The degrees of freedom (358) and the very small t-value (.069) indicate that the means of the two groups are almost the same and the discrepancy is not statistically important. Therefore, Filipino adolescents' academic performance is inversely related to their resilience.

Research Question #3

Do Filipino adolescents with specific resilience factors exhibit significantly different academic performance levels compared to those without these factors?

Table 3: Relationship of Academic Performance to Factors of Resilience

Variables	df	F	Sig.	Interpretation	Decision to Ho
Academic Performance * Resilience	1	11.958	.001 ^b	Significant	Reject the Ho and accept the H1

The data presented in Table 3 shows that resilience factors significantly impact Filipino adolescents' academic performance. An F-value of 11.958 is quite high, and a p-value of 0.001 indicates that the model accounts for a significant portion of the variance in educational achievement. Although, the level of significance means the importance of the flexibility factors. Even though the model is statistically significant, it explains only a diminutive part of the variance, suggesting that other factors not included in this model can also significantly affect academic performance.

DISCUSSION

Filipinos are known survivors of circumstances and strong fighters in desperate situations. Despite facing disappointments and tragedies, they emerge more determined to overcome the odds. Resilience is one of the most outstanding characteristics of Filipinos, who consistently exhibit a positive attitude and the belief that they can triumph over adversity. In this era of technology, Filipino adolescents still have the unwavering

conviction that they can overcome any challenges, such as school achievement. Hence, this study focuses on the relationship between resilience and the academic performance of Filipino adolescents.

The data presented in Table 1.1 indicates that girls tend to have a higher score on resilience in the home connection domains than boys. Research findings have proved that the level of family support that girls enjoy in their academic activities is at a higher level than that enjoyed by their male counterparts. This disparity is often exhibited in various aspects, including parent activity, encouragement, and resource provision in their involvement (Eccles, 1993). For example, mothers are, in most cases, more likely to engage daughters in academic discussions, study facility provision, and school function participation (Hill & Lynch, 1998). For instance, the fact that girls are associated with getting better grades than boys is a factor that explains the higher parental support accorded to girls.

In addition, cultural and societal orientations perpetuate the common myth that girls are more "academically-oriented" than boys, thereby subjecting them to higher investment in their academic success. For example, this can be manifested in terms of expanded opportunities for girls, such as the availability of extracurricular activities, tutoring, and college preparatory programs (Epstein, 1988). This tends to create more opportunities and support for girls, enhancing their academic growth and success.

While much progress has been made in promoting gender equality in education, data indicates that girls in some areas still receive more school support than boys (refer to Table 1.2). Studies have found that teachers tend to provide girls with more positive feedback, offer them more opportunities to participate in class, and hold higher expectations for their academic performance (Sadker & Sadker, 1994). This differential treatment may stem from unconscious biases and traditional gender roles that often associate academic success with femininity (Eccles, 1993). Therefore, it is only fair to say that such trends are not universal and significantly vary from one factor to another, whether it is socioeconomic background, school culture, or individual teacher practices. It is important to ensure a balanced and fair educational environment where all students, regardless of gender, receive the support they need to flourish academically (National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine, 2019). In this respect, work to reduce unconscious bias in pedagogical activities and work on creating an inclusive learning environment will ensure that boys also get the attention and encouragement being offered to girls.

According to the data analysis from Table 1.3, girls stated they are more involved in the community than boys. The academic achievement of teenagers is significantly enhanced by the influence of their peers. Multiple studies have shown that children who spend time with classmates and peers who value education are more likely to be actively engaged, hardworking, and successful in school (Wentzel, 2002). Positive peer pressure can come in many different forms, such as encouraging study habits, providing assistance, or serving as a source of encouragement by setting a good example. Peer groups can also

be informational and knowledgeable resources, foster a sense of community, and increase academic self-efficacy (Wentzel & Asher, 1995).

Similarly to this, peers can play a positive or negative role in academia. Adolescents who associate with disengaged classmates or harbor pessimistic views about learning are at a higher risk of experiencing disengagement from school.

Some research indicates that girls tend to receive more social support from their peers at school than boys (Table 1.4). Among the reasons for attempting to explain this are societal expectations and gendered norms that have associated girls with emotionality and emotional expression. It has been established that girls offer more prosocial behaviors and practices, including supportive emotionality and building closer and more intimate friendships with peers, than boys. These close friends therefore offer a sense of belonging and security, and this relates to elevated well-being and academic performance.

However, it is important to note that this difference in social support does not imply that boys do not experience social support or that they are less capable of offering it. Differences that may be observed may emerge due to the different socialization practices and encouragements of boys and girls in ways of expressing emotions and seeking support (Goodwin, 2002). Schools have a crucial role in this respect in creating supportive and socially inclusive environments for all students, regardless of gender, by promoting positive peer relationships and emotional literacy and providing diverse opportunities for social interaction and connection.

Data analysis shows a notable gender gap in this specific factor of empathy (Table 1.5). Girls' participation increased the number of subscales considered. Moreover, research has shown that girls are more empathetic than boys, an observation linked to a blend of biological and social elements. Studies have revealed that girls are more likely than boys to express and recognize emotions, especially those associated with sadness and distress, from a very young age (Eisenberg & Lennon, 1983). This may result from hormonal factors, with females having high levels of *oxytocin*, a hormone proven to play a role in social bonding and empathy (Taylor et al., 2000).

Societal expectations and gender role stereotypes also strongly influence empathetic development. Girls receive more encouragement to be open about their emotions and to be nurturing and caring, whereas boys receive stronger socialization practices that encourage them to be emotion-suppressing in favor of assertiveness and independence (Eisenberg et al., 2007). Differences in such socialization factors, therefore, affect how empathy is expressed and understood, which could be an explanation for this observed gender gap. To acknowledge the differences between males and females, it also has to be stated that empathy is a complex product that a whole host of other factors can influence.

Studies have found that girls tend to do well in verbal fluency, reading comprehension, and social problem-solving (Table 1.6), while boys may perform better in visual-spatial

reasoning, mathematical skills, and problem-solving involving logical thinking (Hyde, 2005). However, the differences tend to be rather subtle and brought up by cultural expectations and opportunities.

It's important to consider that within each gender group, there is a broad range of individual variations. Socioeconomic background, educational opportunities, and parental support, among many other factors, are known to be significant moderators of the development of problem-solving abilities. Thus, both girls and boys should be provided with a diverse set of learning experiences while fostering a growth mindset where perceived gender gaps are narrowed for the benefit of individual potential (Dweck, 2006).

The concept that girls are inherently more motivated and interested in studies compared to boys (Table 1.7) is a complex one since this is often based on societal expectations and stereotypes. It has been demonstrated that girls tend to do better academically during primary and secondary school, primarily in language arts and social studies, when compared with boys (Hyde, 2005). There is no guarantee, however, that such differences imply a more intense level of inherent motivation. Parental support, teacher expectations, and social influences can significantly affect a child's level of interest and performance in school, regardless of gender.

A further piece of research indicates that boys can be more prone to risk-taking behaviors, which in rare cases might cause a decrease in their academic achievements. But this doesn't exactly make them less motivated or uninterested in learning. It's right to stress that both genders can have quite a wide scope of motivations and interests, which is why a supportive and inclusive learning environment is likely to help all students succeed and reach their full potential.

Challenges often noted for boys, who may mask their underestimation of abilities with lower self-perceptions of academic performance relative to girls (Marsh, 1990), are plausible through a multitude of explanatory routes concerning societal demands on masculinity, peer influences, and the perceived importance of traditionally masculine characteristics of physical and verbal assertiveness. This might mean that boys, also, are encouraged not to undertake "feminine" activities that require much cognitive stimulation.

Solving this problem demands a rather comprehensive approach, including the creation of an all-inclusive and congenial learning atmosphere where boys feel free to express their talents and interests. Teachers and parents can be of immense help in developing a growth mindset concerning boys so that they are allowed to expose their capabilities and encouraged to seek help in areas where they require assistance. In addition, encouraging collaboration and teamwork within academic circles would help negate the stereotype because boys will appreciate teamwork.

Besides, many times, the girls demonstrate a greater degree of motivation and involvement in community programs and initiatives compared to their boys counterparts

(Table 1.9). This can be attributed to various factors, such as greater expectations from society to be nurturing, caring, and empathetic. Perhaps a girl is more likely to identify herself with social causes and hence more duty-bound to effect a positive change in the community. Moreover, in line with research, girls tend to develop more advanced social skills and communication abilities, which can contribute to their comfort and confidence in engaging in group activities and community-based initiatives.

Additionally, girls often have unique challenges and experiences that make them want to advocate for social change. For example, girls may be more aware of gender equality, social justice, and environmental sustainability issues. Such heightened awareness can translate into a strong desire to make a difference in the world. Involving girls in community programs and initiatives is not only beneficial for their development but also encourages a sense of agency and civic engagement, empowering them to positively change the world.

Research has also indicated that girls are likely to have a more favorable perception among peers in many respects compared to boys (Table 1.10), especially concerning social competence, empathy, and emotional intelligence (Goodwin & Watts, 2014). There are various reasons for this trend, including societal expectations regarding the same, which would be much more relevant for girls. More likely, girls engage in prosocial behavior, such as support or displays of kindness, which can contribute to a better reputation among their peers. Additionally, girls may have an advantage in understanding social dynamics and how to resolve conflicts in the process of communication, making their communication smoother and relationships stronger.

In summary of the findings related to research question 1 using the T-Test, data analysis reveals that girls with a weighted average mean of 3.82 are more resilient than boys with a weighted average mean of 3.15. Multiple studies have consistently shown that girls tend to demonstrate greater resilience than boys, particularly in domains such as literacy, numeracy, and overall well-being (Dwiningrum, 2022; Ivonne, 2007; Wasonga, 2002; Shukla, 2009). This trend is often attributed to the presence of stronger support networks, both within the family and in the broader community, for girls compared to boys (Wasonga, 2002). Nevertheless, it is crucial to note that resilience is not solely determined by gender but is also influenced by individual experiences and the learning process (Dwiningrum, 2022).

Furthermore, research by Zacharias (2020) and Sunarti (2018) did not find significant differences in resilience levels based on depressive symptoms, anxiety, region, poverty, gender, or type of school. Additionally, Medina (2019) also found no significant difference in resilience levels among adolescents in a specific educational institution. These findings suggest that while gender may play a role in resilience, other factors such as mental health, socio-economic status, and environmental influences may not significantly impact resilience levels in Filipino adolescents.

Similarly, the study may have been affected by sample bias, as the resilience scales utilized may not have been appropriate for the Filipino cultural context. Cultural elements

such as "pakikisama" (harmonious interpersonal relationships) that impact resilience may not be fully understood. Looking back, the Philippines has an extensive history of dealing with difficulties, ranging from natural calamities to socio-economic hurdles. However, Filipinos are famous for their outstanding resilience, which is their capacity to recover from difficult situations. Factors in Filipino culture that contribute to this resilience include placing importance on the welfare of the community and nurturing robust social connections that offer support in times of hardship. Therefore, it is important in Filipino culture to uphold harmonious interpersonal connections, as this encourages teamwork, resolution of disputes, and a feeling of being part of a community, all vital for overcoming obstacles. A component of Filipino culture involves the "bahala na" mentality, which translates to "leaving it to God" or accepting whatever may come. It may appear passive at times, but it can also be seen as a hopeful acknowledgment of things beyond one's control, enabling adjustment and concentration on finding solutions.

In Filipino culture, there is a significant focus on interpersonal connections, referred to as "pakikipagkapwa-tao," showcasing their resilience. The importance of strong social connections and community support are essential for overcoming difficulties and creating a feeling of inclusion (Enriquez, 1992). Filipinos depend greatly on their families, friends, and communities for emotional backing, practical help, and shared moments, aiding them in dealing with hardship and staying optimistic (Hollnsteiner, 1970). This deeply rooted belief in interconnectedness enables Filipinos to gain strength from their social connections, enhancing their resilience and nurturing a feeling of unity in the face of challenges (Jocano, 1999).

Filipinos are famous for their bravery and determination when confronted with challenges. This quality drives their resolve to conquer obstacles. (Albay, 2021) stated that there are four aspects to Filipino resilience: self-efficacy, positive attitudes towards challenges, cognitive emotion regulation, and future orientation among youth. Additionally, they possess a strong dedication to work and a persistent attitude, which are crucial for overcoming challenges and bouncing back from failures.

In brief, the sample might not represent the broader Filipino adolescent population and could be skewed toward a specific socioeconomic background or geographical location where challenges are less severe. Generally, Filipino adolescents might exhibit a high baseline level of resilience due to cultural values such as family support (kapwa) and a positive outlook (bahala na). This could narrow the range of scores, making it challenging to detect differences between high and low-resilience groups.

It has been demonstrated in this study that resilience factors have a notable influence on the academic achievement of Filipino adolescents, as depicted in Table 3. Findings from Robilla's (2012) research indicated that greater economic and material pressure on children correlates with lower academic performance due to diminished mental and psychological well-being, as well as reduced life satisfaction. Addressing these factors has the potential to empower students and contribute to their educational success. It's

important to remember that resilience goes beyond bouncing back from adversity; it's about perseverance despite challenges.

This suggests that adolescents with specific resilient attributes generally exhibit slightly better academic performance than those without these attributes. Thus, there is compelling evidence indicating the presence of a linear correlation between adolescents with certain factors and those without said factors. The positive correlation (0.179) shows that when one variable increases, the other usually increases as well (and vice versa). Nevertheless, correlation should not be mistaken for causation, requiring additional analysis and interpretation in a specific context is necessary to understand the practical consequences of this relationship.

Consequently, resilience factors like strong social support networks (*kapwa*) and positive coping mechanisms can help adolescents manage academic stress more effectively, leading to better focus and concentration during studies. In total, cultural values like “*sipag at tiyaga*” and a strong sense of family obligation can motivate students to persist through academic challenges and achieve their goals. Factors such as strong family connections, support systems, and a sense of belonging fostered by “*pakikisama*” can contribute to higher self-esteem and confidence, as these can translate into a more positive attitude toward learning and a willingness to take academic risks. Ultimately, resilience can help adolescents cope with personal challenges that might otherwise lead to absenteeism. This allows for consistent participation in classes, which is important for academic progress.

Conclusions

This research investigates through quantitative methods, how resilience and academic performance are linked in Filipino adolescents. It analyzes how gender may relate to resilience within the school setting. Although the results indicate that girls might show more academic resilience than boys, a deeper understanding is needed. Teen girls often present a higher level of empathy, aspiration, and community engagement core to academic success. This might cause them to attend more school activities, go on field trips, access study help, and also the various academic programs. These children frequently strengthen their working relationships with peers regarding their social roles to be more capable of and ready to assist others. In contrast, boys potentially showing more autonomy and independence may experience difficulties asking for help and in doing so, may cooperate less in the way they learn. While both sexes are being supported more or less similarly by the school community and their problem-solving skills are even similar, their social expectations and the consequences for their personalities can affect their academic success in the end. To begin with, managing emotions, having strong social support, and believing in oneself are complex concepts of resilience. To pinpoint and understand where gender disparities may be most visible, future studies need to explore this specific aspect. Do girls excel at reaching out to peers or teachers for assistance? Are they equipped with more effective methods for managing their emotions? These questions need to be looked into more closely. Secondly, the effect of other factors, like

sociocultural factors, must be considered. Gender biases, cultural norms, and school settings can all influence the development of academic perseverance. Expectations to adhere to conventional ideas of masculinity could prevent boys from asking for assistance or showing weakness, which could impede their ability to bounce back from challenges. Likewise, educational systems that perpetuate these stereotypes may accidentally put boys at a disadvantage.

It seems that while resilience factors do influence academic performance, the data does not show significant differences in academic outcomes between adolescents categorized as having high or low resilience. The results showed a modest but statistically significant positive relationship, indicating that teenagers with high and low resilience levels do not differ significantly in their academic performance, and resilience factors are connected to academic performance in teenagers. This suggests that while resilience contributes to academic success, it does not necessarily differentiate academic performance among those with varying levels of resilience. It appears that other factors such as support systems, learning environments, and personal circumstances may play a more critical role in influencing academic performance among adolescents. Therefore, fostering resilience should be part of a broader strategy that addresses multiple aspects of a student's life to effectively support their academic journey.

This implies that Filipino adolescents with greater resilience generally achieve higher academic success, although the impact may be small. The weak connection suggests that other variables may also have a considerable influence, though these findings can reinforce the increasing focus on resilience in achieving academic success. Further studies could investigate these factors, like economic status, the availability of educational materials, and teaching strategies concerning academic success among the students. Furthermore, the small impact size highlights the multifaceted characteristics of resilience, and while promoting resilience is beneficial, it may not be the only way to enhance academic achievement. Studying certain aspects of resilience that are most strongly linked to academic success could be productive. This research also provides important insights into how resilience influences academic achievement in teenagers. Although the correlation is positive, it is important to recognize its limitations and examine how other elements interact. Understanding this delicate connection allows educators, guidance counselors, and policymakers to create a more comprehensive approach and plans that help teenagers succeed academically.

To summarize, this research provides a simple start to a nuanced discourse that gives insight into a possible gendered feature of academic resilience by recognizing the various dimensions of resilience and the impact of social and cultural factors, which is vital for understanding its whole character. Further research and investigation into these intricacies may lead to the development of more specific interventions that promote resilience in every student, regardless of gender, and can help students overcome academic obstacles and excel in their educational journey by fostering this valuable quality in every person. This research contributes to understanding the factors that determine academic success in the Philippine context. The emphasis on resilience sets the foundation for applying strategies and treatments to develop it.

Recommendations

Cultural characteristics of coping and support systems are validated for Filipino adolescents to ensure that samples include participants from various socioeconomic backgrounds, regions, and experiences that can be considered in employing resilience scales in future research. In addition, mixed methodologies can be used to obtain insights into the lived experiences of adolescents with different levels of resilience and follow teenagers to see how resilience affects their mental health, academic achievements, and other outcomes.

Even if there are no statistically significant differences between the groups, a qualitative approach may show practical discrepancies, making it beneficial to investigate additional factors that influence and promote resilience, such as religious views, resource availability, and coping techniques. Future research can provide a more nuanced picture of resilience among Filipino adolescents by addressing these issues. This insight can help design programs aimed at promoting resilience and positive mental health in this population.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This research study adheres to the highest ethical standards, following established guidelines. Participants were informed about the study's purpose, procedures, and potential risks. Confidentiality and anonymity were maintained throughout the study.

Data collection followed ethical guidelines and relevant institutional policies. Personal identifiers were removed from the datasets to ensure privacy, and the data was securely stored and accessible only to authorized researchers.

The study has one major author (myself) and two co-authors. Authorship was determined based on substantial contributions to the research. All authors participated in the data analysis using SPSS.

Moreover, no conflict of interest exists among the authors. The researchers declare no financial or personal relationships that could bias the study. In addition, the study received no external funding, and all data collection, analysis, and publication costs were self-supported. Hence, the researchers are committed to upholding ethical principles and ensuring the integrity of our research.

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